

Equilibrium Constants of Copper(II)-Acetyl Acetone and Copper(II)-N-Benzoyl Phenyl Hydroxylamine Complex Systems in Various Mixed Aqueous Solvents

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Equilibrium constants of complex systems between cupric ion and ligands : acetyl acetone (ACAC) and N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxyl amine (NBPHA) are measured in various mixed aqueous solvents viz. water-dioxan, water-isopropanol, water-acetone, water-ethanol and water-methanol. The solvent compositions are 50% v/v for ACAC and 75% v/v for NBPHA, at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and 0.1M NaClO₄ ionic strength. Equilibrium constants $\beta_n = \frac{[ML_n][H]^n}{[M][HL]^n}$ are first determined and then the formation constants

$\beta_n' = \frac{[ML_n]}{[M][L]^n}$ are calculated. The values of formation constant in aqueous dioxano nly are compared with the reported values in literature. Correlation between $\log \beta_n$ values vs $1/\epsilon$ is not observed in different solvents, where as some regularity of log of formation constants vs $1/\epsilon$ is observed in different solvent media.

ACETYL acetone (ACAC) and N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxyl amine (NBPHA) are two widely acclaimed organic reagents used in analytical chemistry. It appears that ACAC has only one enolic OH which is dissociable and NBPHA has got one OH group. So both can be regarded as monoprotic ligands. The purpose of the present paper is to apply the methods for monotropic ligands¹⁻³ on these reagents to measure the metal ligand equilibrium constants in various mixed aqueous solvents viz. water-dioxan, water-isopropanol, water-acetone, water-ethanol and water-methanol. Copper(II) ion is used as the central metal ion.

The alkali titration curves indicate that both the ligands are practically undissociated when the complexes are formed. So the reaction takes the course,

So the free ligand concentration is measured by the expression¹ (charges are omitted)

$$[HL] = (T_{HL}^0 - \bar{n}T_M^0) \left(\frac{V^0}{V^0 + V^m} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

The symbols have usual significance. And the equilibrium constant

$$\beta_1 = \frac{[CuL][H]}{[Cu][HL]} \text{ and } \beta_2 = \frac{[CuL_2][H]^2}{[Cu][HL]^2}$$

are directly calculated by the expression¹

$$\sum_{n=0}^{n=\bar{n}} (\bar{n} - n) \beta_n \frac{[HL]^n}{[H]^n} = 0 \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n} - 1)} \frac{[H]}{[HL]} (= Y) \text{ is plotted vs } \frac{(2 - \bar{n})}{(\bar{n} - 1)} \frac{[HL]}{[H]} (= X)$$

in large graph papers and points falling on approximate straight line are used for calculation. The constants are computed by Burroughs 6700 system. Here essentially the standard least squares technique is adopted. But it is so programmed that several least square values of constants are obtained by considering several sets of experimental points. Finally the mean of the several values is found out and standard deviation calculated.

The formation constants β_1' are also calculated by the relation

$$\beta_1 = \frac{[CuL]}{[Cu][L]} \frac{[H][L]}{[HL]} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\therefore \log \beta_1 = \log \beta_1' - \log pK_1^H \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{and } \log \beta_2 = \log \beta_2' - 2 \log pK_1^H \quad \dots (5)$$

Experimental

E. Merck, G. R. quality ACAC and NBPHA were used. The pH measurements were made at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

0.04M copper perchlorate was prepared⁴ as stock solution. 0.02M solution ACAC and 0.01M solution NBPFA were prepared in the particular solvents.

pH titrations were done with the following solutions.

(1) Mineral acid—This contained 0.0025M HClO₄ and 0.1M NaClO₄ in 20 ml of the various solvents; (2) Ligand solution—This was the same as mineral acid solution but contained 0.005M ligand in addition and (3) Metal solution—This was the same as ligand solution containing in addition 0.001M cupric ion.

The metal : ligand ratio was maintained at 1 : 5, and the solutions were titrated with 0.1M carbonate free NaOH solution. The titration cell was flushed with pure nitrogen gas previously saturated with the particular solvent used in the reaction cell.

Results and Discussion

The equilibrium constants were directly determined from the expressions (1) and (2) and are shown in Tables 1 and 2. Formation constants were also calculated by the relations (4) and (5) and so pK₁^H values were also determined.

Correlation between true [H] and B values :

This was determined by titration 0.0025M HClO₄ in the particular solvent in presence of 0.1M NaClO₄ with 0.1M NaOH. Near the neutralisation point the alkali was diluted ten to twenty times and titration continued. B values were plotted against the calculated [H] in the particular medium.

Proton ligand formation constant :

The values of pK₁^H were measured with the help of the expression,

$$\log pK_1^H = B + \log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)$$

and following usual procedure^{4*}

$\log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A}$ vs B was plotted and straight lines

were obtained having almost unit slope. pK₁^H values are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

It can be seen (Table 1) that the log pK₁^H values for ACAC in different media has the following order :

Stability of the ligand conjugate acids increase with the decrease in dielectric constants, position of isopropanol being anomalous. The values of log pK₁^H for NBPFA in different solvent mixtures (Table 2) has the following order :

This is almost as before except that the position of dioxane and acetone is reversed.

Acetyl acetone complex :

The copper(II)-ACAC system is studied in 50% v/v water-solvent composition. The values of dielectric constants of the solvents are either obtained or calculated from the data given by Hall *et al*⁵, and Akerlof⁶. Log β (equilibrium constant), log β' (formation constant) values are shown in Table 1. The plot of Y/X are good sloping straight lines. In most cases even in very low B values \bar{n} values are hardly <1. The values of constants when arranged in increasing order for the different media reveal the following sequences,

For log K₁ :

For log β₂ :

For log K₁' :

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cu(II) COMPLEXES OF ACETYLACETONE IN 50% (v/v) MIXED AQUEOUS SOLVENTS AT 30° ± 0.1° AND 0.1M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH

Solvents composition	Reciprocal of D.C. (1/ε)	log of equilibrium constants		log pK ₁ ^H	log of formation constants	
		log K ₁	log β ₂		log K ₁ '	log β ₂ '
50% v/v Dioxan-water	0.0298	1.98 ± 0.03	2.41 ± 0.02	9.72 ± 0.01	9.10 ± 0.04	17.85 ± 0.04
„ Isopropanol-water	0.0219	1.62 ± 0.01	2.43 ± 0.004	9.35 ± 0.01	8.97 ± 0.02	17.13 ± 0.024
„ Acetone-water	0.0198	1.56 ± 0.01	2.16 ± 0.01	9.56 ± 0.01	9.12 ± 0.02	17.28 ± 0.03
„ Ethanol-water	0.0194	1.59 ± 0.01	2.22 ± 0.004	9.34 ± 0.01	8.93 ± 0.02	16.90 ± 0.024
„ Methanol-water	0.0178	1.59 ± 0.004	2.12 ± 0.003	9.27 ± 0.01	8.86 ± 0.014	16.66 ± 0.023

TABLE 2—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS AND FORMATIONS CONSTANTS OF Cu(II) COMPLEXES OF N-BENZOYL PHENYL HYDROXYL AMINE IN 75% (v/v) MIXED AQUEOUS SOLVENTS AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ AND 0.1M NaClO₄ IONIC STRENGTH

Solvent composition	Reciprocal of D.C. ($1/\epsilon$)	Log of equilibrium constants		$\log pK_1^H$	Log of formation constants	
		$\log K_1$	$\log \beta_2$		$\log K_1'$	$\log \beta_2'$
75% v/v Dioxan-water	0.0699	1.74 ± 0.004	2.42 ± 0.00	10.59 ± 0.01	10.33 ± 0.014	19.60 ± 0.024
„ Isopropanol-water	0.0359	1.92 ± 0.02	2.56 ± 0.01	9.83 ± 0.01	9.75 ± 0.03	18.22 ± 0.03
„ Acetone-water	0.0289	1.57 ± 0.03	2.0 ± 0.02	10.67 ± 0.01	10.24 ± 0.04	19.34 ± 0.04
„ Ethanol-water	0.0271	1.73 ± 0.01	2.54 ± 0.01	9.74 ± 0.01	9.47 ± 0.02	18.02 ± 0.03
„ Methanol-water	0.0230	1.73 ± 0.02	2.38 ± 0.01	9.57 ± 0.01	9.30 ± 0.03	17.52 ± 0.03

For $\log \beta_2'$:

methanol < ethanol < isopropanol < acetone < dioxane

Clearly the sequences for equilibrium constants are at random and they have no relation with the dielectric constants of the media. But formation constants increase with decrease of dielectric constant except that the positions of isopropanol and acetone are reversed.

Values of formation constants in aqueous dioxane are available in literature : $pK_1^H = 9.70$ (at 30° ; 50% dioxan)^{7,8}, $\log K_1' = 9.55$, $\log \beta_2' = 17.68$ (at 30° , 50% v/v dioxan)⁷, for Cu(II)-ACAC ; $\log K_1' = 9.40$, $\log \beta_2' = 17.43$ (25° , 50% v/v dioxan, 0.3M ionic strength)⁹ for Cu(II)-ACAC. $\log \beta_2'$ for Cu-ACAC complex was calculated to be 17.4 in 50% v/v dioxan¹⁰. Our values at 30° and 0.1M ionic strength are closely similar. The values of constants in other solvents are not very different.

N-Benzoyl phenyl hydroxyl amine complex :

The copper(II)-NBPHA system is studied in 75% v/v solvent-water composition. With 50% v/v composition with all the solvents except dioxane (here also the range is small) precipitation commences at very low B values. (Dioxane at 4.20, acetone at 2.78, ethanol at 3.0, methanol at 2.72 and isopropanol at 3.10).

Therefore higher solvent proportion 75% v/v is employed. For 75% composition precipitation commences a little before the following B values : dioxane 9.70, isopropanol 4.40, acetone 4.38, ethanol 4.66, methanol 4.46. Once again the starting \bar{n} values are hardly less than 1 and Y/X curves are quite good straight lines. The values of the constants may be arranged in the increasing order for the different media. The following sequences are found :

For $\log K_1$:

acetone < methanol < ethanol < dioxane < isopropanol

For $\log \beta_2$:

acetone < methanol < dioxane < ethanol < isopropanol

For $\log K_1'$:

methanol < ethanol < isopropanol < acetone < dioxane

For β_2' :

methanol < ethanol < isopropanol < acetone < dioxane

The sequences for equilibrium constants are at random and have no correlation with dielectric constants of the media. But formation constants increase with decrease of dielectric constant except that the positions of isopropanol and acetone are interchanged.

Shome *et al*¹¹ have measured formation constants of metal NBPHA system for Al³⁺, Ga³⁺, In³⁺, La³⁺, Y³⁺ etc. They reported $pK_1^H = 10.10$ at 25° and 50% v/v dioxane. Bag *et al*¹² reported $pK_1^H = 10.05$ at 25° and 50% v/v dioxane and for copper complex $\log K_1' = 9.46$ and $\log \beta_2' = 17.44$. They used half integral method. Majumdar *et al*¹³ reported $pK_1^H = 9.8$ in 50% ethanol at 22.5° and Ryan *et al*¹⁴ have found $pK_1^H = 10.45$ and for copper complex $\log K_1' = 10.3$ and $\log \beta_2' = 18.7$ in 50% v/v dioxane at 25° .

Thus considering our experimental conditions the values fairly agree with the published data. The absence of correlation between the equilibrium constant $\log \beta_1$ or $\log \beta_2$ vs $1/\epsilon$ may be explained by the following factors which may have counteracting influences on the $\log \beta$ values. These are (a) dielectric property of the mixed solvent, (b) proton solvation in different solvents, (c) ion-pair formation, (d) metal ion solvation by the organic solvent and (e) ligand solvation.

For formation constant values factor (b) and to some extent (c) is absent. This explains some amount of regularity of $\log \beta_1'$ values vs $1/\epsilon$ of the solvent media.

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